

**Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling
Ionospheric Disturbances Effects**

TechTIDE

Report on TID activity metrics definition

Version 1.0

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Abstract

The deliverable presents a report on the TID activity in TechTIDE. It contains results from the TID detection methods, the additional geophysical information for overall assessment of current conditions, and the classification of the TID activity. There is also specification of statistical limits based on which, the TID disturbance are characterized as unimportant, weak, moderate and intense. This deliverable presents the Report on TID activity metrics definition.

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Executive Summary

TechTIDE project, funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 research and innovation program [AD-1], will establish a pre-operational system to demonstrate reliability of a set of TID (Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances) detection methodologies to issue warnings of the occurrence of TIDs over the region extended from Europe to South Africa. TechTIDE warning system will estimate the parameters that specify the TID characteristics and the inferred perturbation, with all additional geophysical information to the users to help them assess the risks and to develop mitigation techniques, tailored to their application. This document is a report for the TID activity metrics definition of the different TID detection methods in TechTIDE.

1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document presents the TID activity report of TechTIDE. The document contains results of the TID detection methods, the additional geophysical information for overall assessment of current conditions, and the classification of the TID activity. Statistical limits will be specified based on which, the TID disturbance will be characterized as unimportant, weak, moderate and intense. The document is divided into four sections:

Section 1 (the current section) describes the purpose of this document and its organization.

Section 2 lists the applicable and reference documents and also contains the list of acronyms used in this document.

Section 3 presents a summary of the TIDs algorithms in TechTIDE and a classification of the TID activity for the respective methods.

Section 4 presents a first evaluation of the results of the TID detection methods, reporting methods' results for events analyzed in retrospective analysis and reports for real-time detected events.

Section 5 is the summary and concluding section providing a summary of the TID activity metrics and results, including a specification of statistical limits, based on which the TID disturbance are characterized with different levels of importance for different methods and categories. It presents also a summary of the TechTIDE Activity Report and of the cross-validation and evaluation of the detection methods based on the assessment of current geospatial and lower atmosphere conditions.

2. Associated documents

2.1. Applicable Documents

The following table contains the list of applicable documents.

Table 1. List of applicable documents

AD	Document title
[AD-1]	Grant Agreement number: 776011 — TechTIDE — H2020-COMPET-2017

2.2. Reference Documents

The following table contains the list of references used in this document.

Table 2. List of reference documents

RD	Document title
[RD-1]	Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances Effects TechTIDE D2.1 Report on the design and specifications of the TID algorithms and products

RD	Document title
[RD-2]	Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances Effects TechTIDE D2.2 Report on TID algorithms
[RD-3]	Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances Effects TechTIDE D3.2 Report on TID drivers
[RD-4]	Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances Effects TechTIDE D5.2 Statistical Analysis of the Results
[RD-5]	Manuel Hernández-Pajares, J. Miguel Juan Zornoza, Jaume Sanz, " <i>Medium Scale Traveling Disturbances Affecting GPS Measurements: Spatial and Temporal Analysis</i> ", Journal of Geophysical Research, Space Physics, Vol.111, A07-S11, 2006, (doi:10.1029/2005JA011471).
[RD-6]	Juan J.M, J. Sanz. A. Rovira-García, G. González-Casado, D. Ibáñez and R. Orús Pérez (2018). AATR an ionospheric activity indicator specifically based on GNSS measurements. J. Space Weather Space Clim. 2018, 8, A14. doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2017044 .
[RD-7]	Warning and Mitigation Technologies for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances Effects TechTIDE D4.3 TechTIDE warning system. Second Release

2.3. Acronyms

The following table contains the list of all acronyms used in this document.

Table 3. List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
2D	2-Dimension
3D	3-Dimension
AATR	Along-arc TEC rate
BGD	Borealis Global Designs Ltd.
CDSS	Continuous Doppler Sounding System
DLR	German Aerospace Center
DPS4D	Digisonde-Portable-Sounder-4D
EDD	electron density distribution
EGNOS	European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service
FU	Frederick University
GBAS	Ground Based Augmentation System

Acronym	Definition
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HF	High Frequency
HF-INT	HF-Interferometry
HTI	Height-time-reflection intensity
IAP	Institute of Atmospheric Physics (Academy of Sciences of Czech Republic)
IdN	Identification Number
LSTID	Large Scale TID
MSTID	Medium Scale TID
MUF	Maximum Usable Frequency
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
OE	Fundació Observatori de l'Ebre
OI	Oblique Incidence
OTHR	Over The Horizon Radar
PFA	Probability of false alarm
POD	Probability of detection
ROT	Rate of TEC
Rx	Receiver
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SSA SWE	Space Situational Awareness Space Weather
SSBC	Solar Sector Boundary Crossing
SSN	Sunspot Number
TEC	Total Electron Content
TID	Travelling Ionospheric Disturbance
Tx	Transmitter
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
VI	Vertical Incidence
WP	Work-package

3. TID detection methods: Classification of the TID activity

This section presents the TIDs algorithms in TechTIDE, as summarized in Table 4. Detailed description of the original concept, design, and updates for each of the methodologies is provided in TechTIDE Deliverable D2.1 [RD-1] and Deliverable D2.2 [RD-2]. Identification of the most important TID drivers and additional parameters required to be exploited for the development of the warning system are provided in TechTIDE Deliverable D3.2 [RD-3]. Classification of the TID activity for the respective methods of detection are discussed below in sections 3.1-3.8.

Table 4. Summary of TechTIDE TID identification methodologies. Green background: real-time capability, yellow: transition to real-time in progress.

IdN. Method	Main Characteristics	Intermediate Product	Final Product	Value added Product
1. HF-TID Detects perturbations in space from all possible sources (solar and lower atmosphere origin) and it is suitable for the identification of both MS and LS TIDs	<u>Input:</u> signal properties from Digisonde synchronized operation. <u>Output:</u> TID velocity, amplitude, propagation direction at the signal reflection point between the stations	Doppler frequency, angle of arrival, and time-of-flight from Tx to Rx, both OI and VI sounding	Separately for MS and LS TID: 1+ detections of {TID Period, Phase Velocity, Direction of propagation, Wavelength, and Amplitude}	Maps of the current TID activity Maps of TID occurrence probability
2. HF-INT Finds oscillation activity in ionospheric characteristics and it can detect LSTIDs only.	<u>Input:</u> ionospheric characteristics from VI and OI soundings. <u>Output:</u> 2D TID vector velocity, amplitude and period.	De-trended ionospheric characteristics and contribution of LSTID to the data variability.	Dominant period, Amplitude and 2D Vector velocity of detected LSTID.	Estimation of LSTID propagation
3. MSTID index Can detect perturbations in space from all possible sources (solar and lower atmosphere origin) and it is suitable for the identification of MSTIDs	<u>Input:</u> GNSS TEC from single receivers over a region. <u>Output:</u> Fluctuations associated to the MSTIDs and estimation of the propagation parameters (direction, velocity and amplitude).	De-trended GNSS data measurements.	TID Velocity, Direction of propagation and Amplitude	Climatology and physical origin of MSTID
4. GNSS TEC Gradient Analyze TEC maps and it is mostly sensitive to perturbations from LSTIDs.	<u>Input:</u> Grids of TEC maps over a region. <u>Output:</u> Latitude-time maps of TEC gradients and indication of significant gradients.	Maps of TEC and TEC rate	TEC Gradients	Graphical presentation in an image

IdN. Method	Main Characteristics	Intermediate Product	Final Product	Value added Product
<p>5. Single location LSTID index</p> <p>The index is derived comparing the detrended electron density with the standard deviation of the values included in the median calculation.</p>	<p><u>Input:</u> the electron density distribution calculated with the TaD code over each Digisonde.</p> <p><u>Output:</u> The detrended electron density (dNe) at various altitudes.</p>	The relative standard deviation of the dNe values, RSDNe.	The relative standard deviation, RSDNe, at pre-defined heights (200, 300, 400, 500 km).	LSTID activity index at pre-defined heights (200, 300, 400, 500 km).
<p>6. HTI</p> <p>Detects LSTID activity in the F-layer virtual height over a Digisonde station.</p>	<p><u>Input:</u> raw vertical ionogram binary data from a single Digisonde station</p> <p><u>Output:</u> Period and virtual height amplitude of LSTID activity over the Digisonde station.</p>	F region virtual height variation above a Digisonde station	Period and virtual height amplitude of dominant LSTID activity.	Map indicating LSTID periodicity over various Digisonde stations
<p>7. CDSS-MSTID</p> <p>Analyze Doppler shift of radio signals to detect quasi-periodic perturbations and associate them with overpassing MSTIDs.</p>	<p><u>Input:</u> CDSS reflected signals, ionospheric characteristics and irregularities.</p> <p><u>Output:</u> Doppler shift, SNR and confidence level.</p>	Continuous Doppler shifts of fixed sounding radio frequency.	Period, Amplitude and Phase of Doppler measurements.	MSTIDs Characteristics Seismic response
<p>8. AATR Indicator</p> <p>Analyze TEC data over specific region and it is mostly sensitive to ionospheric perturbations at different time scales</p>	<p><u>Input:</u> slant TEC parameters.</p> <p><u>Output:</u> the Along Arc STEC Rate, metric to characterize the ionosphere operational conditions of EGNOS.</p>	TEC rate	Warning of ionospheric activity.	Warning about the availability in SBAS systems
<p>9. Ionospheric background conditions</p> <p>Provides maps of the difference of the current electron density in respect to the running median conditions at various altitudes for the European region.</p>	<p><u>Input:</u> the electron density distribution calculated with the TaD code (a) the current values at each grid point of the mapping area (Europe), (b) the running median values at each grid point of the mapping area</p> <p><u>Output:</u> The difference between the current and the median values at each grid point.</p>	3D ED grids with the corresponding running median.	Ionospheric Background Activity conditions over the area are estimated depending on the spatial coverage of median, positive and negative conditions.	Pixel maps indicating the perturbation of the electron density in respect to median conditions in color codes. The maps are calculated at the altitudes of 200, 300, 400 and 500 km.

3.1. HF-TID

This method detects TIDs, provides TID Period, Phase Velocity, Direction of propagation, Wavelength, and Amplitude, and evaluates as main parameter the Amplitude of the detected perturbation in respect to the ambient electron density (AMP %), propagation velocity and azimuth. TID is commonly described as a wave-like moving modulation of the ionospheric plasma density that affects traversing radio signals. The amplitude of such density modulation is generally proportional to the severity of the impact on system operations. However, there are different ways of defining the amplitude of TID wave. Correspondingly, there may not be a universally applicable, consistent method to associate a “TID amplitude” with the “TID impact” across various sensor instruments and across different user applications.

As far as the HF-TID technique is concerned, the instrument-bound TID activity metric is well established. HF-TID is sensitive to the quasi-periodic variations of the HF radio signal recorded on an oblique Digisonde-to-Digisonde (D2D) links. Once such quasi-periodic signal behavior is detected, HF-TID uses the observed signal to infer properties of the TID wave responsible for the variation. The TID wave amplitude A_N is one of such HF-TID derived properties, readily available for categorization and presentation to the user. A_N is defined formally under assumption of a simple TID model in which, for any particular fixed altitude z_0 in the ionosphere, TID is a sinusoidal perturbation of the background density $N_0(x, y, z_0, t)$ in time t and horizontal plane (x, y) :

$$N(x, y, z_0, t) = N_0(x, y, z_0, t) \left[1 + A_n(z_0) \cos \left(\Omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda} \vec{r} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

Here TID wave is characterized by its amplitude $A_N(z_0)$, angular frequency Ω , and wavelength Λ , while the phase distance \vec{r} depends on direction of TID travel in the horizontal plane, Θ :

$$\vec{r} = x \cos \Theta + y \sin \Theta \quad (2)$$

TID is commonly interpreted and presented as the *surface undulation* in space and time, and therefore it would be more intuitively to characterize it in terms of the vertical displacement of the isodensity surface with the undulation amplitude A_c (rather than the background density modulation in the horizontal plane at z_0 with the perturbation amplitude A_N). However, HF-TID community has accepted Eq.(1-2) definitions in order to remain compatible with existing raytracing algorithms that use $N(x, y, z, t)$ specifications to evaluate TID impact on the sensor signal. Therefore, for historic reasons, activity metrics for the HF-TID method are defined in terms of A_N . The perturbation amplitude A_N is related to the undulation amplitude A_c via

$$A_N(z_0) = \frac{1}{N(z_0)} \frac{\partial N}{\partial z} A_c(z_0) \quad (3)$$

Because HF-TID detects the quasi-periodic signal variations on a particular radio-link between two Digisondes, thus derived TID amplitude A_N is specific to a particular signal reflection area in the ionosphere, located at specific altitude z_0 above the mid-point between two ends of the link (transmitter and receiver). Clearly, naturally occurring TID waves do not span all altitudes in the ionosphere with the same perturbation $A_N(z_0)$. While model considerations can be

devised to reason about the altitude dependence of $A_N(z)$ on $A_N(z_0)$, the HF-TID technique does not actually provide direct evaluations of the altitude extent of TID wave from the D2D observations.

Therefore, while HF TID has been proven to be sensitive to even minute undulations caused by the traveling disturbance, that determination is pertinent to a very particular area in the ionosphere. This makes estimation of the impact of the end user operations even more difficult, as these systems exhibit different sensitivity to the plasma disturbances of different extent in space, both in the vertical and horizontal dimensions. Unfortunately, this means that there is no universal TID activity metric definition that would suit all systems.

The perturbation amplitude $A_N(z_0)$ is an excellent candidate for a consistent and objective characterization of the TID phenomenon as evaluated by the HF-TID technique. It has a clear physical meaning and well defined minimum and maximum values. For an easier interpretation, $A_N(z_0)$ is given in %, thus ranging from 0 to 100%.

Current version of HF-TID defines five levels of LSTID activity in relation to the detected amplitude; **Insignificant** activity for events with $AMP < 5\%$, **Weak** for events with $5\% \leq AMP < 10\%$, **Moderate** for events with $10\% \leq AMP < 15\%$, **Strong** for events with $15\% \leq AMP < 20\%$, and **Very Strong** activity for events with $AMP \geq 20\%$. Current product of the HF-TID is shown in the Figure 1. Current version of the HF-TID method is under revision and therefore, because of low confidence, no azimuth information are given in the report.

Figure 1. Example of the HF-TID product in the real-time TechTIDE warning service for a given scenario.

Next step in defining TID activity metrics is to assign the range of $A_N(z_0)$ values into subcategories for presentations to each user application, as well as to the data analysts.

The following arguments for such categorization were used to design the presentations.

- From experience operating HF-TID, the quiet-time level of the wave activity in the ionosphere is about 4-5%. Should there be a “No TID in progress” category introduced, 4-5% would be optimal cutoff value.
- Study of the “EGU Opening Event” storm-time HF-TID data suggests that detected $A_N(z_0) = 40\%$ wave was visible in GNSS observations as a minor-to-moderate storm event. Should a “Moderate TID” category be introduced, it should be positioned at that level.
- There is no need to use more than one activity category above the “Moderate TID” as it may confuse the user. If data analyst desires to locate periods of the highest TID activity, a query of TID database can be easily arranged to select $A_N(z_0)$ above, say, 75%.
- If a two-category classification (“GO” and “NOGO”) is preferred for certain user applications, the center of the “Moderate TID” category shall serve as the cutoff value for “GO” category.

Given these considerations, the following three systems are implemented (Table 5):

Table 5. Three TID Activity Metrics systems for HF-TID method.

System #1		System #2		System #3	
Category	Amplitude	Category	Amplitude	Category	Amplitude
NOGO	> 40%	Strong	> 60%	Strong	> 60%
GO	< 40%	Medium	30-60%	Medium	30-60%
		Weak	< 30%	Weak	5-30%
				None	< 5%

3.2. HF-INT

HF-Interferometry (HF-INT) is a method to identify LSTIDs for the monostatic measurements of a given network of HF sensors (Ionosondes). The spatial distribution of the network should be dense enough to detect LSTID; i.e, distance between measuring sites no larger than 1000 km. The method detects quasi-periodic oscillations of ionospheric characteristics, identifies coherent oscillation activity at different measuring sites of the network and sets bounds to time intervals for which such activity occurs into a given region. The disturbance potentially associated to TID in the last 6-h interval will be related to the de-trended ionospheric characteristics after removing the main daily harmonics. The dominant period of oscillation and amplitude of the LSTID are obtained by spectral analysis. This allows for identification of TID activity from Digisonde Networks. The vector velocity of propagation is estimated by the measured time delays of the disturbance of a given ionospheric characteristic at different sensor sites and assuming a plane wave propagation. Due to the geographical distribution of Digisonde sites within Europe and South Africa (some of the sensors are separated by about 1000 km from one to the other), only identification of LSTIDs is feasible in principle, which are associated with auroral and geomagnetic activity, directly related to Space Weather. We refer the reader to Deliverable D2.1 [RD-1] and Deliverable D2.2 [RD-2] for more details.

The HF interferometry method uses the Maximum Usable Frequency (MUF) obtained from 10 European Digisondes and 4 Digisondes from South Africa (see Figure 2). It uses near real time data from the GIRO DIDBase Fast Chars (<http://giro.uml.edu/didbase/scaled.php>).

Figure 2. Geographic locations of the Digisonde stations used in the HF-INT method for Europe (left) and South Africa (right) network.

Classification of the TID activity for the HF-INT method is related to the *Spectral Energy Contribution* (SEC) of the detected TID. We refer the reader to Equations 8-9 in [RD-2], which shows that SEC of a given LSTID to the total spectral energy is equivalent to the contribution of the LSTIDs to the total variability for a given time series. Thus, the larger SEC of a LSTID, the larger impact of a LSTID to the variability. First release of the method HF-INT method defined four levels of LSTID activity: $SEC < 10\%$ for **Insignificant** LSTID, $10\% \leq SEC < 50\%$ for **Weak**, $50\% \leq SEC < 80\%$ for **Moderate** LSTID, and $SEC \geq 80\%$ for **Strong** LSTID. HF-INT method defined also an arrow length scale according to the magnitude of the propagation velocity of the LSTIDs (Figure 3). In addition, HF-INT provided information when no enough data is available in the network to detect LSTIDs.

Figure 3. Example of the HF-INT product in the real-time TechTIDE warning service for a given scenario over Europe network.

Based on the retrospective analysis done for 2018 and for the European network, we have made some statistics to define additional level of LSTID activity and corresponding thresholds. The different levels of activity and thresholds are obtained from the distribution of the cumulative number of events for a given SEC or lower (Figure 4, right). The first decile of the distribution defines the threshold between Insignificant and Weak activity. The second quartile of the distribution defines the threshold between Weak and Moderate. The third quartile defines the threshold between Moderate and Strong, and the ninth decile defines the threshold between Strong and Very Strong activity. Thus, we define **Insignificant** activity for events with $SEC < 18\%$, **Weak** for events with $18\% \leq SEC < 65\%$, **Moderate** for events with $65\% \leq SEC < 80\%$, **Strong** for events with $80\% \leq SEC < 86\%$, and **Very Strong** activity for events with $SEC \geq 86\%$. Left plot in the Figure 4 depicts the results of the distribution of all events detected over all the sensors of the European network. Note that the number of detected events correspond to about 9% of the total number of cases analyzed. The latter values will be applied to the second release of the HF-INT method in the TechTIDE repository which is expected for the last trimester of 2019. Although not fully shown here, the statistics presented in the Figure 4 have been discriminated for different regions of the European network (Figure 4, right) and for different season and different local time sectors. Comparisons provides similar results to those shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 4. The plot at the left depicts the distribution of the percentage of occurrence of LSTID events detected by the HF-INT with a SEC lower than a given value and definition of the thresholds of SEC that define the different levels of activity for weak (green), moderate (yellow), strong (orange) and very strong (red). Note that insignificant level is set to those cases where no coherent activity has been detected or when $SEC < 18\%$. The right plot compares the above distribution for different regions of the European network.

3.3. Spatial and temporal GNSS analysis

It was shown in [RD-4] the relationship between the degradation in the performance of a NRTK service and the presence of MSTIDs, where the presence of the TIDs was characterized by means of a MSTID index ($MSTID_{idx}$) for each transmitter-receiver pair. Indeed, in the study, it

was demonstrated that users with a single frequency receiver can achieve a significant reduction of their positioning error by using just observations with $MSTID_{idx} < 0.01$ LI metres (being LI the geometry free combination of carrier phases, i.e. $LI=L1-L2$).

$MSTID_{idx}$ looks for ionospheric perturbations with time scales from some minutes to tens of minutes, which are the typical periods of MSTIDs. According to its definition in [RD-1], $MSTID_{idx}$ varies largely depending on the receiver location. For instance, Figure 5 depicts a statistic of the $MSTID_{idx}$ for a receiver at high latitude (KIRU) and a receiver at mid latitude (EBRE). The statistic is done using the complementary of the Cumulative Distribution Function (1-CDF), i.e. the probability of being the $MSTID_{idx}$ larger than a specific value. The time series cover a period of nearly 1 year from 2018 (DoY 291) up to 2019 (DoY 241).

As it can be seen, the activity at high latitude is much more pronounced than at mid latitude, being the $MSTID_{idx}$ larger than 0.01 LI metres in around the 10% of the cases. On the other hand, unlike high latitude, ionospheric activity at these time scales is, in general, very low at mid latitude.

Figure 5. Complementary of the CDF for 2 receivers, KIRU and EBRE, during one year of data starting on 2018 DoY 291.

However, NRTK service, with single frequency receivers, requires high accuracy in the ionospheric corrections, thus it can be affected by perturbations with only some tenths of a TECU of amplitude. In this sense, as was seen in [RD-4], observations with $MSTID_{idx} > 0.01$ LI meters (i.e. around 0.1TECUs) affects the positioning error.

The data for the study done in [RD-4] was gathered by the CATNET network -a NRTK network operated by the Institute Geologic and Cartographic of Catalunya (IGCC)- during a period of 11 years. However, it was only possible to process 2 periods of these 11 years: the 1-year period 2008-2009 and the 2-years period 2017-2019. The Figure 6 depicts the statistic for $MSTID_{idx}$ for all the receivers in CATNET during these periods.

Figure 6. Complementary of the CDF for all the receivers in the CATNET. The data covers a 2-years period from 2017 to 2019 (red) and a 1-year period from 2008 to 2009 (green).

As it can be seen, the MSTID activity is similar during the two periods. However, as it was shown in [RD-5], MSTID activity has several temporal dependencies (for instance, with local time and season). These dependencies are also studied in the context of the WP6 in order to provide models for mitigating MSTID effects on NRTK service. In spite of the small values of the index, the number of observations with $MSTID_{idx} > 0.01$ LI meters, i.e. affecting NRTK service, is around a 3%. Notice, that this is a global figure which varies largely along the day or the season.

In conclusion, NRTK services can be affected by MSTID activity with $MSTID_{idx} > 0.01$ LI metres. This is in spite of $MSTID_{idx}$, statistically, the usual values of $MSTID_{idx}$ can reach much more high values. Current product of the MSTID indicator is provided in the Figure 7.

Figure 7. Example of the MSTID product in the real-time TechTIDE warning service for a given scenario.

3.4. GNSS TEC gradient

GNSS TEC gradients are not a direct measure of TIDs. Therefore, it is not applicable to classify TID occurrence based on TEC gradients. Instead, TEC gradients are considered to be a precursor for LSTID activity. Strong ionosphere-thermosphere perturbations in high-latitudes, which are generating the LSTIDs, are considered to be reflected in significant TEC gradients. Such TEC gradients associated to the generation of LSTIDs are typically observed in the Auroral region, which is over Europe in the latitudinal band between 60 and 70°N.

An example of the correlation between the TEC gradients and LSTID occurrence is shown in Figure 8, which presents time-latitude plots at 10°E. In this case, TEC gradients are rather weak. Therefore, we used geometry TEC measurements to estimate the TEC gradients as precise as possible. The comparison between the LSTID occurrence in the detrended TEC and the TEC gradients shows that significant TEC gradients occur in high-latitudes (55-70°N) prior to the passage of LSTIDs in mid-latitudes.

Figure 8. Upper panel: Detrended TEC amplitudes. Slanted rays reflect the passage of LSTIDs. Lower panel: TEC gradients derived from geometry free TEC estimates.

For operational purposes, the fastest and most efficient approach is currently implemented. This is the estimation of TEC gradients based on TEC maps. Since the generation of TEC maps averages out steep TEC gradients, rather low thresholds have to be assumed for the indication of the probability of LSTID generation.

For the estimation of thresholds for the TEC gradients, probability density functions and cumulative density functions have been derived from TEC gradient maps for the year 2017. The results are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Left: Probability Density Function (PDF) for TEC gradients derived from IGS TEC maps in the European region during the year 2017. The PDFs are shown for different latitudes with different colors. The legend describes the geographic latitude in °N. Right: Complementary of the Cumulative Distribution Function (1-CDF), derived from the PDFs. The grey lines show the thresholds at 90, 95 and 99% probability. The TEC gradients amplitude is given in mm/km.

The statistical analysis of TEC gradient show, that the average TEC gradient has an amplitude of about 0.2 mm/km. Generally, TEC gradients are larger in high-latitudes. Since the LSTIDs are generated by strong dynamics in high-latitudes (in the Auroral oval), only high-latitude TEC gradients are considered to act as precursor for LSTID occurrence. The alarm thresholds are derived based on the 90. 95 and 99% quantile, derived from the complementary of the CDF of the high-latitude region. TEC gradients are considered low with amplitudes below 1.2 mm/km, moderate with amplitudes above 1.2 mm/km and below 2 mm/km and strong above 2 mm/km.

3.5. LS TID Index

The TechTIDE warning system provides dynamic plots of the LSTID activity index for the last 24 h over each Digisonde sensor with the analytical data of the current RSD. The plots are generated for indicative heights: 200km and 400km. Corresponding values in ASCII are also provided.

The relative standard deviation RSD of the detrended electron density data is the quantity based on which the index is calculated. The scaling of the activity level is defined based on the correlation between the AATR index and the RSD at each Digisonde location.

The LSTID activity index is preliminary derived based on the following criteria:

RSD<100 the LSTID index=0 (No TID)

100<RSD<300 the LSTID index=1 (Uncertain Conditions)

RSD> 300 the LSTID index=2 (TID)

The criteria for the definition of the LSTID index scales will be finalized considering the correlation results between AATR and the RSD for a large number of events and for different Digisonde locations (see for example the results in Figure 10. The correlation cannot be one-to-one for two reasons mainly because the RSD is calculated from the vertical electron density profile at a specific location, whereas AATR refers to perturbations detected over the field of view of each specific receiver. Therefore an AATR spike can be caused by a disturbance detected hundreds of kilometers far away from the GNSS receiver. Consequently the correlation between AATR and the RSD can be only qualitative.

Figure 10. Example of the RSD (%) variability on 7 and 8 September 2017 over Dourbes at 200 km altitude, plotted together with the AATR index at Reykiavik (red) and Kiruna (blue).

3.6. HTI

The height-time-reflection intensity (HTI) algorithm enables the identification of the LSTID periodicity over each Digisonde station participating in the TechTIDE project by using the actual ionograms produced at each station. This technique considers an ionogram as a “snapshot” of reflected intensity as a function of virtual height and Digisonde signal frequency, and it uses a sequence of ionograms to compute an HTI plot, (for a given frequency bin). The final optimized version of the technique as used in the TechTIDE project exploits multiple narrow frequency bins to overcome interference causing gaps on ionogram traces. For each frequency bin at each time interval we obtain a value of the virtual height with an appropriate uncertainty (as the standard deviation). This is more reliable than the previous implementation of the HTI technique which relied on wide (1 MHz) frequency bin determined by using auto-scaled foF2 data from Digisondes. The virtual height variation on various frequency bins is then reduced to a representative signal by removing from each the average background and a statistical fitting technique is then applied in order to examine how well a sinusoidal model describes the data. This approach reduces spurious variations of the virtual height and can clearly indicate when the signal is trust worthy. In order to obtain a measure for the level of activity we performed an analysis for year 2017 over the European stations where all measured LSTID activity was available. Absence of LSTID activity in the presence of a clear virtual height signal is termed as Insignificant otherwise an indication will be given when no enough data is available in the network to detect LSTIDs. We then define four levels of LSTID activity according to the four quartiles of the detected events. (**Weak**, **Moderate**, **Strong** and **Very Strong** LSTID) as illustrated in Figure 11. Each quartile represents a particular range of amplitudes which is expected to be station dependent.

Figure 11. Example of the statistical analysis performed for the classification of LSTID activity based on HTI. On the left we show the collected amplitudes for all events (this example is for EB049) during 2017. The right part shows the cumulative distribution function of these events and the classification according to the four quartiles.

3.7. CDSS-MSTID

The Czech ionospheric CDSS-MSTID method consisting of five well-spaced local networks demonstrates broad possibilities of monitoring and investigation of atmospheric gravity wave activity related to different sources and their ionospheric signatures (e.g., ionospheric infrasound, MSTIDs). This method detects MSTIDs and provides TID Period, Amplitude (AMP) and Phase of the Doppler measurements [RD-1]. Figure 12 shows calculation results of the observed wave period on the 3 MHz radio path Panska Ves (transmitter) – Prague (receiver) during the passage of strong tropospheric front on March 19, 2017. The enhanced MSTID activity is well seen from at about 16:00 UTC.

Figure 12. The enhanced atmospheric wave activity on March 19, 2017, observed on the CDSS 3MHz sounding path between Panska Ves and Prague, Czech Republic (700 min is at about 15:40 UTC). Observation of waves with periods 5min to 30 min are shown on the left side and 10 min to 40 min on the right side of the plot.

CDSS observations indicated much high wave activity on 29 July 2005, day of strong stormy convection, than on quiet days (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Fourier spectrum calculated for 29 July 2005, day of strong tropospheric convection above Prague. Thick line: amplitude spectrum on 29 July 2005. Thin line: median of Fourier spectra on quiet days. Dashed lines are for lower quartile and upper quartile of Fourier spectra on quiet days.

For detection of MSTIDs the CDSS provides direct Doppler shift measurements (or inputs for further calculations) of the wave period, amplitude, phase velocity and direction of propagation (azimuth). The Figure 14 presents the characteristic Doppler shift record on 20 June, 2013.

Figure 14. The Czech CDSS Doppler shift record obtained on June 20, 2013 for the radio path of the frequency 3.59 MHz from 18:00 till 24:00 UTC.

Analysis of a selected interval from 20:30 to 22:00 showed the MSTIDs propagated to the North-East (azimuth $\sim 45^\circ$). The probable source was the thunderstorm which coming from the South - West and passed through the western part of the country.

We aware that AGWs of different periods and originated from different sources are practically permanently present in the Earth's atmosphere. Utilizing CDSS Doppler shift measurements we are able obtain period, amplitude, phase velocity and direction of wave propagation. Our about 15 years-long experience in Doppler measurements and expertise of wave effects on ionospheric variability allow us to define following characteristic/parameter scales: Doppler shift ($\Delta f < 0.06\text{Hz}$) – MSTID activity is **insignificant**; when the Doppler shift is ($0,06 < \Delta f < 0,12$) activity is **moderate**; when Δf is ($> 0,12 \text{ Hz}$) the activity is **strong**. Horizontal propagation velocity obtained from the measurements is attached to single levels: 1st level $<100 \text{ m/sec}$; 2nd level: $100 - 199 \text{ m/sec}$; 3rd level: $200 - 350 \text{ m/sec}$; 4rth level: $>350 \text{ m/sec}$.

Latest parameters/characteristics of the wave activity over the Czech Republic, as it is shown in the Table 6, could be obtained via the website <http://tid.ufa.cas.cz/>.

Table 6. Information on the parameters/characteristics of the atmospheric wave activity as it is provided on the IAP CDSS website. Spectrogram on the left is visualization of the Doppler shift measurements for the morning hours of January 30, 2019.

Time (UT)	State	Horizontal velocity (m/s)	Azimuth (°)	Period (min)	Oscillation velocity (m/s)
2019-01-30 10:45:00	TIDA	88.1±5.68	102.2±1.25	21.5±9	21.31±8.35
2019-01-30 10:30:00	TIDA	109.9±9.77	124.5±34.98	21.5±10	13.80±7.70
2019-01-30 10:15:00	TIDA	139.8±37.05	158.9±14.4	25.4±5	14.99±6.71
2019-01-30 10:00:00	TIDA	284.4±177.76	149.3±31.63	112.7±32	12.83±5.42
2019-01-30 09:45:00	TIDA	117.5±11.72	152.6±3.28	16±2	12.51±5.71
2019-01-30 09:30:00	TIDA	54.1±42.36	184.8±10.46	16±5	19.34±6.25
2019-01-30 09:15:00	TIDA	176.7±194.37	285.2±30.58	18.3±3	15.63±7.96
2019-01-30 09:00:00	TIDA	76.5±27.66	268.2±31.45	30.2±9	18.08±7.70
2019-01-30 08:45:00	TIDA	121±19.55	181.3±11.29	31±9	18.41±8.06
2019-01-30 08:30:00	TIDA	222.3±153.92	181.8±16.39	31.2±9	19.31±8.48
2019-01-30 08:15:00	TIDA	336.8±108.09	146.5±19.27	31.5±9	16.15±9.54

3.8. AATR indicator

As an example of the different AATR values since the beginning of the TechTIDE project (2017), the Figure 15 depicts the AATR statistic for three different receivers at different latitudes (see coordinates in the figure). The statistic is done during the period 2017-2019 by means of the complementary of the CDF (1-CDF), i.e. the probability of being the AATR larger than a specific value.

Figure 15. Complementary of the Cumulative Distribution Function (1-CDF) during the period 2017-2019 for 3 different receivers: KIRU (high latitude), BRST (mid latitude) and MAS1 (low latitude).

As it can be seen, large AATR values are more probable for the high latitude receiver KIRU, where the 1% of the data present AATR values greater than 0.5 TECUs/min. On the contrary, for the low latitude receiver MAS1 there is a low probability of having large values of AATR. However, as it is seen in [RD-6], AATR depends also on the solar cycle and one has to take into account that the period 2017-2019 is around the minimum of the solar cycle. Finally, for the receiver at mid latitude, BRST, there are not large AATR values during this period. A complete analysis about the AATR dependencies for hundreds of receivers can be found in [RD-6].

As it can be seen in [RD-4] or in [RD-6], AATR can be used for defining ionospheric activity linked to the performance degradation of the EGNOS performance. These studies establish a threshold of around 0.5 TECUs/min for moderate activity and around 1.0 TECUs/min for high ionospheric activity. Current product of the AATR indicator is provided in the Figure 16.

Figure 16. Example of the AATR product in the real-time TechTIDE warning service for a given scenario.

3.9. Ionospheric Background Conditions

This method evaluates as main parameter the deviation of the current electron density map from the running median electron density map. The method can be used for the identification of the background conditions (i.e. negative or positive storm events) and assess the possibility to detect ionospheric disturbances. For periods of very low background electron density, the possibility to detect TIDs is small because the amplitude of TID perturbation is directly proportional to the background electron density (Hooke 1968). Classification of the activity and their corresponding scales are derived by comparing the current deviation (dNe) of the electron density from its median from the standard deviation (1σ), at each point of the grid of the map and at different altitudes covering the range from 200km to 500 km, applying a color code as follows:

- $|dNe| < 1\sigma$ median conditions
- $dNe > 1\sigma$ positive
- $dNe < -1\sigma$ negative

Ionospheric Background Activity conditions over the whole region is specified according to the following criteria:

- Median conditions are dominating: Green points $> 80\%$
- Positive conditions are dominating : Red points $> 80\%$
- Negative conditions are dominating : Blue points $> 80\%$
- Conditions tend to be disturbed: positive and negative points $>$ median points
- Conditions tend to be median: positive and negative points $<$ median points

In the mapped region (Figure 17), the area covered by Digisonde observations, is delimited in latitude and longitude by the four stations at its edges, Chilton, Ebro, Athens and Juliusruh. This area includes the 80% of the mapped region. Therefore the 80% percentage is critical to characterize conditions over Europe.

Figure 17. Maps of the residuals of the current electron density in respect to median conditions with color scales in respect to positive and negative effect. The Maps are calculated at 200km, 300km, 400km and 500 km. This example shows only the map at 200km (left) and 400km (right).

3.10. Classification of the detection methods and TID activity metrics

The above 9 methodologies which feed the [TechTIDE warning System](#) [RD-7] can be grouped into three categories:

- Ionospheric disturbance **indicators**: AATR, GNSS TEC Gradient and Background Activity Maps.
- LSTID detection methods**: HF-TID, HF-INT, LSTID index and HTI.
- MSTID detection methods**: MSTID index and CDSS MSTID.

Note however that **HF-TID**, **HF-INT**, and **HTI** could afford to detect MSTIDs if data-sampling and network topology of the sensors could be dense enough.

According to the above specifications, the classification of the TID activity and metrics are summarized in Table 7, Table 8, and Table 9 for disturbance indicators, LSTID detection methods and MSTID detection methods respectively.

Table 7. Summary of TechTIDE classification activity and metrics for the different **indicators** of ionospheric disturbance.

Method	Product	Characteristic/Parameter: Scales
GNSS TEC Gradient	<u>TEC gradient map</u> : Absolute value of the gradient (Amplitude) expressed in mm/km	<u> TEC Gradient Amplitude in high-latitudes (57-67°N) </u> : [< 1.2] Low [$1.2, < 2$] Medium [> 2] Strong
AATR Indicator	<u>Activity Index</u> : AATR expressed in TECU/min	<u>AATR</u> : [< 0.5] Low [$0.5, < 1$] Medium [> 1] Strong

Method	Product	Characteristic/Parameter: Scales
Ionospheric Background Conditions Indicator	<p><u>Detection of background ionospheric activity including positive and negative ionospheric storm effects</u></p> <p>Color coded maps of the deviation of the current electron density in respect with median electron density.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $dNe < 1\sigma$ median conditions (green) ▪ $dNe > 1\sigma$ positive (red) ▪ $dNe < -1\sigma$ negative (blue) 	<p><u>Ionospheric Background Activity conditions Characteristics:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Median conditions are dominating: Green points > 80% ▪ Positive conditions are dominating : Red points > 80% ▪ Negative conditions are dominating : Blue points > 80% ▪ Conditions tend to be disturbed: positive and negative points > median points ▪ Conditions tend to be median: positive and negative points < median points

Table 8. Summary of TechTIDE TID classification activity and metrics for the different LSTID detection methods.

Method	Product	Characteristic/Parameter: Scales
HF-TID	<p><u>Detections of TID:</u></p> <p>Period, Phase Velocity, Direction of propagation, Wavelength, and Amplitude (expressed as % of the perturbation in respect to the ambient electron density)</p>	<p><u>Amplitude:</u> [$<5\%$] Insignificant [5%, $<10\%$] Weak [10%, $<15\%$] Moderate [15%, $<20\%$] Strong [$>20\%$] Very strong</p> <p><u>Velocity:</u> 1st level <100 m/sec 2nd level: $100 - 299$ m/sec 3rd level: $300 - 999$ m/sec 4th level: >1000 m/sec</p> <p><u>Azimuth:</u> TBD</p>
HF-INT	<p><u>Detections of LSTID:</u></p> <p>Period, Spectral Energy Contribution (SEC), Velocity, Direction of propagation</p>	<p><u>SEC:</u> [$<18\%$] Insignificant [18%, $<65\%$] Weak [65%, $<80\%$] Moderate [80%, $<86\%$] Strong [$>86\%$] Very Strong</p> <p><u>Velocity:</u> 1st level <100 m/sec 2nd level: $100 - 299$ m/sec 3rd level: $300 - 999$ m/sec 4th level: >1000 m/sec</p> <p><u>Azimuth:</u> TBD</p>
LSTID index	<p><u>Detection of LSTID:</u></p> <p>Perturbation in the local values of the electron density (RSD%) at specific altitudes (from 200 to 500 km) and specific geographic locations.</p>	<p><u>RSD:</u> <100 LSTID index=0; No TID $100 < RSD < 300$ LSTID index=1; Uncertain Conditions $RSD > 300$ LSTID index=2; TID</p>

Method	Product	Characteristic/Parameter: Scales
HTI	<u>Detection of LSTID:</u> Period and virtual height amplitude of LSTID over each Digisonde station.	<u>Virtual height amplitude:</u> [<5 km] Insignificant [5, < 10 km] Weak [10, < 15 km] Moderate [15, < 20 km] Strong [> 20 km] Very strong

Table 9. Summary of TechTIDE TID classification activity and metrics for the different MSTID detection methods.

Method	Product	Characteristic/Parameter: Scales
MSTID index	<u>Activity Index:</u> MSTID_idx expressed in m of LI (1 TECU=0.105 m of LI)	<u>MSTID_idx:</u> [<0.1] Low [0.1, <0.2] Medium [>0.2%] Strong <u>NRTK:</u> [<0.01] Quiet
CDSS-MSTID	<u>Detections of MSTID:</u> Period, Amplitude, Phase velocity, Direction of propagation	<u>Doppler shift:</u> [<0,06] Insignificant [0,06, <0,12] Moderate [0,12, <018] Strong <u>Velocity:</u> 1st level <100 m/sec 2nd level: 100 - 199 m/sec 3rd level: 200 - 350 m/sec 4th level: >350 m/sec <u>Azimuth:</u> TBD <u>Coherency:</u> 0-1

4. Results of the TID detection methods

This section presents a first evaluation of the results of the TID detection methods. Although the near-real-time detection methods and warning system and of TechTIDE are available since April 2019, the TechTIDE methods can run both in a retrospective and real-time analysis. Following subsections reports about results of the TID detection methods for specific events. Section 4.1 reports for events analyzed in retrospective analysis and section 4.2 reports for real-time detected events.

4.1. September 2017 ionospheric perturbation events

A series of disturbances occurred in September 2017, initiated with a solar flare on 6 September. [RD-4].

4.1.1. Impact on navigation systems

The research group of Astronomy and GEomatics (gAGE/UPC) has analyzed the impact of the solar flare occurred in September 6th of 2017 (day of year 249) in three navigation systems: EGNOS (the European SBAS system), PPP and NRTK.

As it was reported by several services that are monitoring the space weather events, during day 249 in 2017, a Solar Flare of class X9.3 was occurred around noon (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Solar activity of 6 September 2017. Plot gathered from SpaceWeatherLive.com.

This Solar Flare produced a sudden increase of the ionization and, from the point of view of GNSS, a sudden increase of the STEC for all satellites in view during noon. Indeed, Figure 19 (bottom) shows this sudden increase of the STEC associated to the measurements from several satellites collected by receivers at very different places (Canary Islands, Spain and Iceland). This simultaneous increase of STEC allows to define a GNSS based monitor of Solar Flares as it is depicted in the top plot of the Figure 19.

Figure 19. Sudden increase of the STEC for all satellites in view during noon related the solar flare of 6 September 2017 (bottom) and Solar Flare detection base on the GNSS TEC rate (top).

Associated with the Solar Flare, EGNOS availability presented a clear drop on its availability, as can be seen in the plots reported by ESSP in the Figure 5 of the [RD-4] and also in the hourly availability maps computed with the GLAB tool (Figure 20).

Figure 20. SBAS availability map provided by GLAB tool of UPC for given hour in September 6th 2017.

Related with the Solar Flare, AATR values present a moderate increase on its values but in all the region of the South of Europe (Figure 21 and Figure 22).

Figure 21. AATR index for 6-8 September 2017 for given mid-high latitude GNSS receivers in Europe.

Figure 22. AATR index for 6 September 2017 for given mid-high latitude GNSS receivers in Europe.

In the Figure 21, one can see that there is a moderate increase of the AATR at noon of day 249, these values are much more moderate than the values during days 250 and 251 that are associated to the ionospheric storm that occurs when the particles ejected by the Sun during the Solar Flare arrives to the Earth 1.5 days later.

Despite of such moderate values of AATR, the impact on the EGNOS service was not negligible (Figure 20).

4.1.2. Irregularities observed in the ionosphere

A Coronal Mass Ejection was associated to the solar flare occurred on September 6th 2017, which produced a significant impact in the EGNOS performance on the two following days, the 7th and 8th of September. We refer the reader to Figure 5 of [RD-4] and related text for further details. If we focus on September 8th, the values of geomagnetic index Kp and rate of TEC index can perfectly match with the EGNOS availability degradation in the North of Europe (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Geomagnetic activity index kp (left) for 6-8 September 2017, and TEC rate index of high latitude stations for 8 September 2017 (middle).

Geomagnetic Dst activity index showed strong storm started on 7 September and the recovery phase expand till 10 September (Figure 24).

Figure 24. The Dst index for September 2017.

The analysis showed that the EGNOS degradation is linked to the GPS L2 loss of lock by some receivers in the North caused by a high TEC gradients produced by the impact of the CME in the upper atmosphere. Additionally, this CME generate different type of irregularities in the ionosphere like TIDs and TEC gradients.

The LSTID activity as observed by the HF-INT for 7 September of 2017 (day 250) reports a dominant disturbance for all the European stations with a periodicity of about 2-h and clear southward propagation occurring in the day-time and in the evening to mid-night hours (Figure 25). Above the Dourbes station (DB049) in Belgium, Juliusruh (JR055) in Germany, and Ebro (EB040) in Roquetes, Spain, the disturbance was first detected on September 7 at about 8:00 UT and lasted for about 6 h. It repeated again by 20:00 and lasted for about 3 h. The disturbance in the morning propagated with an azimuth of 170° (from true north) and a velocity of about 800m/s. Stations in South Africa observe a dominant disturbance with a periodicity close to 1.5-h and clear northward propagation occurring in the evening (Figure 25). Above the Hermanus station (HE13N), the disturbance was first detected on September 7 at about 14:00 UT and lasted for about 6-7 h. The disturbance propagated with an azimuth of 350° (from true north) and a velocity of about 300m/s. These are typical characteristics of a LSTID whose origin might be auroral.

Figure 25. LSTID detected by the HF-INT method for 7 September 2017. See text above for details. The length and direction of the arrows indicates the velocity and azimuth of the disturbance respectively.

A LSTID activity was also observed for 8 September of 2017 (day 251) for all the European stations occurring in early hours, as continuation of the event reported for 7 of September (Figure 26). After 2:00 UT, we do not observe any significant activity for the European stations. However, we should notice that data availability for European stations was not good enough for the HF-INT method, mainly caused by the presence on strong Es layers that screened F-region observations. The disturbance in the night of 7-8 September propagated with an azimuth of 180° (from true north) and a velocity of about 400m/s. South African stations report a dominant disturbance with a periodicity of about 1.5-h and northward propagation occurring in the day-time hours (Figure 26). Above the Louisvale station (LV12P), the

disturbance was first detected on September 8 at about 10:00 UT and lasted for about 4 h. The disturbance propagated with an azimuth of 0° (from true north) and a velocity of about 450m/s. These are typical characteristics of a LSTID whose origin might be auroral.

Figure 26. LSTID detected by the HF-INT method for 8 September 2017. See text above for details. The length and direction of the arrows indicates the velocity and azimuth of the disturbance respectively.

Large scale TID detection methods based on GNSS measurements revealed lots of TID activity during 7th and 8th September 2017 over Europe (Figure 27). There were rather fast and large waves during daytime on the 7th September. During morning and afternoon hours on the 8th September slower waves are observed. They are associated to strong energy input from the solar wind.

TEC gradients are a new product of the TechTIDE services, which are provided in near real-time since May 2019. The analysis of the TEC gradients for the September 2017 event show that weak TEC gradients are present during the generation time of LSTIDs. An example is shown in the Figure 28. TEC gradients in the auroral region are suggested to be used as an indicator for the generation of LSTIDs.

TEC gradients in lower latitudes are generated by other mechanisms and are not associated with LSTID activity.

Figure 27. Perturbation TEC for 7 to 8 of September 2017 as provided by DLR.

Figure 28. TEC map and TEC gradient for of September 2017 as provided by DLR.

The HF-TID method in TechTIDE shows a LSTID on JR-PQ path at about 00:00 to 04:00UT on 7th September with WaveAmplitude of 61.8% and WavePeriod of 155 minutes; a MSTID on JR-PQ path at about 13:50 to 14:30UT on 7th September with WaveAmplitude of 58.0% and WavePeriod of 40 minutes; and LSTIDs on EB-AT radio path on 07th September between 22:40-00:50 UT and on 08th September between 14:50-15:48 UT with periods of 65-70 minutes.

The HTI technique has detected strong LSTID activity on the 7 September 2017 over northern European stations (Dourbes (DB049) Belgium, Juliusruh (JR055) Germany, Pruhonice (PQ052) Czech Republic and Fairford (FF051) UK and also in Ebro (EB040) in Spain) with a periodicity ranging from 100 to 120 min during 10:00 UT to 16:00 UT and also during 22:00 UT to 00:00 UT (Figure 29). Weak LSTID activity was also registered with similar periodicities over more southern stations (San Vito, Athens and Nicosia). The HTI technique also detected weak LSTID

activity over South Africa stations during the evening after 20:00 UT as shown in the plot corresponding to Hermanus (HE13N).

Figure 29. LSTID detected by HTI on the 7 September 2017.

Moderate to weak LSTID activity was also detected on the 8 of September 2017 over European stations in the early morning hours, as shown over Ebro (EB040) in Figure 30. South African stations also exhibited moderate LSTID activity during noon to afternoon hours. Above Louisvale (LV12P), the disturbance was first detected at about 13:00 UT and lasted until 17:00

Figure 30. LSTID detected by HTI on the 8 September 2017.

The Ionospheric background conditions are assessed using the results of the maps that show the deviation of the electron density in respect to median conditions for the altitude of 200 km. The two maps of Figure 31 show the effect of the Sudden Storm Commencement recorded by the Dst Index the early morning hours of the 7th September 2019. The effect in the ionosphere is positive due to the superfountain effect.

Figure 31. Maps calculated with the Ionospheric Background Conditions method.

The evolution of large-scale ionospheric storm effects from 7 September at 11UT until the next day is presented in the maps of Figure 32 that demonstrate the drastic changes of the ionospheric storm time effects from positive (red) to negative (blue).

Figure 32. The evolution of ionospheric storm-time effects on 7 and 8 September 2017.

CDSS MSTID indicator detected TIDs with periods higher than 60 min on 7 September between 17:45-19:45 UTC. The horizontal velocity of the observed perturbations was 184-307 m/s, and the azimuth was 53.6°.

Near-real-time detected TID events

The HF-INT method is running in near real time at the TechTIDE project website http://techtide.space.noa.gr/?page_id=3766 since 16th April 2019. Ever since then, the HF-INT has detected several periods of activity.

4.2.1. Event 23-24 April 2019

A significant large-scale Traveling Ionospheric Disturbance (LSTID) activity was detected for the night of 23-24 April 2019. No strong auroral activity was observed for these days and k_p index reached maximum values of 3 only. However a weak activity is observed in the satellite environment as provided by NOAA with some undulations in the magnitude of the magnetic field intensity parallel to the geomagnetic field and in the magnitude of the electron flux. A SSBC was observed late on 23 Apr which caused several periods of unsettled early into 24 April. (Figure 33).

Figure 33. Satellite environment provided by NOAA/SWPC Boulder, CO USA for 22-24 April 2019, updated at 11:31 UTC of April 24.

A clear LSTID with a southward propagation was detected in Europe by the HF-INT method. Above the Ebro station (EB040) located in Roquetes, Spain, the disturbance was first detected on April 23 at about 22:00 UT and lasted for more than 4 hours (Figure 34, left). The disturbance above Europe had a period of about 110 min. and propagated with an azimuth of 180° (from true north) and a velocity of about 600m/s (Figure 34, right). These are typical characteristics of a LSTID whose origin might be auroral.

Figure 34. LSTID detected by the HF-INT method for 23-24 April 2019, updated at 11:11 UTC of April 24. See text above for details. The length and direction of the arrows indicates the velocity and azimuth respectively.

Using the Along Arc TEC Rate – AATR monitor, it is observed a strong ionospheric activity (values of the index AATR greater than 1 TECU/min) in the auroral region at the end of the Day of Year (DoY) 113 (April 23th). However, it is noticeable this activity is quite concentrated on time and in the auroral region, in such a way that AATR in the subauroral receivers is quite moderated. This is illustrated in the Figure 35 using data for stations located in Kiruna, Sweden (21° E, 68° N), Arjeplog, Sweden (15° E, 66° N) and Trondheim, Norway (10° E, 63° N).

Figure 35. AATR index observed for 21-26 April 2019 at indicated high latitude GNSS receivers.

At around midnight of the 23 to 24 April it was observed a strong expansion in the westward auroral electrojet as shown in the IL plot from the IMAGE magnetometer network (Figure 36). Such conditions can certainly trigger TID activity in European mid-latitudes. Moreover, based on preliminary heliospheric modeling carried out at NASA Community Coordinated Modeling Center/Space Weather Research Center, it was issued a warning informing that it was estimated that a CME may impact Parker Solar Probe (glancing blow) and STEREO B (glancing blow) for this day. The leading edge or flank of the CME will reach Parker Solar Probe at 2019-04-23T18:00Z and STEREO B at 2019-04-25T16:00Z (plus minus 7 hours).

Figure 36. IL plot from the IMAGE magnetometer network for 23 to 25 April 2019.

The Large scale TID detection algorithms based on GNSS reveal hardly any LSTID activity during 23rd to 25th Apr. 2019. TEC perturbations are detected in high latitudes during the nights from the 23rd to 24th and 24th to 25th April. These correspond well with the AATR amplitudes presented in the Figure 35 and they also correspond well with the auroral activity presented in Figure 36. There are very weak TEC perturbation signatures that can be single LSTIDs at around 3 UT on the 24th and 25th April, that follow the auroral activity (Figure 37). Dotted lines in the Figure 37 indicates a weak single pulse LSTID with period of about 120 min. and phase speed of about 540 m7s. On the 25th April in the evening hours there are rather weak perturbations in the auroral region, but no LSTIDs.

Figure 37. TEC perturbations for 23-25 April 2019 as provided by DLR.

The HF-TID method in TechTIDE observed strong activity after 3:20 UT of 24 April, lasting for about one hour only as observed in the DB-OE path (4725kHz). Also JR-PQ path at 2475 kHz indicated LSTID passage between 00:00- 04:00 UTC with WP 70 min, and WL 638 km. Moreover, JR-PQ path at 5050 kHz sounding indicated a LSTID with WP 180 min, and WL 2232 km occurring between at about 15:00-18:00 UTC. In addition, the PQ-SO path at 2475 kHz observed LSTIDs on 23-24 April between 23:30-06:00 UTC with WP180 min, and WL 1060 km and on 25 April between 02:00-05:00 UTC with WP180 min, and WL 1638 km.

LSTID activity was detected over Europe by HTI. Above Ebro station (EB040) Spain, the disturbance was first detected on April 23 at about 22:00 UT and lasted for about 4 hours (Figure 38, left). LSTID activity over European Digisonde stations was characterized by wave periods of about 100-110 min. (Figure 38, right).

Figure 38. HTI detection of LSTID over Europe for 23 to 24 April 2019.

Passages of TIDs with periods higher than 60 min have been observed over west part of the Czech Republic by CDSS on 23 April between 15:15-16:45 UTC and 18:00-22:00. Horizontal velocity of the disturbances was 169-545 m/s, with azimuth of 67.1° and 171.3° respectively. On 24 April no LSTIDs were recognized with by CDSS method. (Figure 39)

Figure 39. Wave activity observed over the western part of the Czech Republic on afternoon-evening hours of 23 April (figure on the left) and 24 April 2019 on CDSS sounding frequency of 4.65 MHz.

4.2.2. Events in June 2019

The ionosphere above Europe since early May has been characterized by the presence of strong Sporadic Es-layers, which screen the ionospheric F-region. This makes not possible to detect and monitor TIDs by the HF-Interferometry method (HF-INT) of Tech_TIDE. However, the activity of strong Es was reduced for few days of June, allowing to detect some TIDs events.

This way, HF-INT detected the some TID activity of a dominantly northward propagating TID for the night of 3-4 of June (Figure 40, left) and for the night of 4-5 of June (Figure 40, right). The movie available at https://twitter.com/Tech_TIDE/status/1137038538766200832 shows the northward propagating event observed from 00:20 to 1:45 UT of 4 of June 2019. At a first

glance HF-TID method in TechTIDE shows some activity from 00:00 to 00:40 as observed in the DB-OE path (4725kHz) and in the JR-PQ path (2450 kHz). The activity manifests till 03:45 UT.

The movie available at https://twitter.com/Tech_TIDE/status/1137038979549863938 shows the southward propagating event observed by HF-INT method from 23:20 of 4 of June to 3:00 UT of 5 of June 2019. HF-TID method in TechTIDE also observed strong activity from 21:00 of 4 June to 04:00 of 5 June in the DB-OE path (4725kHz) and as observed in the JR-PQ path (2450 kHz) being more stable for the DB-OE path.

Figure 40. Snapshots for the disturbance propagation of the LSTID detected by the HF-INT method for the night of 3-4 June 2019 (left) and for the night of 4-5 June 2019 (right).

On 4 June the CDSS method detected LSTIDs with periods larger than 60 min passing southward over the western part of the Czech Republic with horizontal velocity ranging from 202 m/s to 398 m/s between 19:15-23:30 UTC (Figure 41).

Figure 41. LSTID activity observed over the western part of the Czech Republic on afternoon-evening hours of 4 June 2019 on CDSS sounding frequencies of 3.59 MHz (on the left) and 4.65 MHz (on the right).

CDSS recorded passage of LSTIDs also on 5 June propagating in north-west direction with velocities in the range 98-399 m/s during the time period 17:15-22:15 UTC and propagating in south-east direction with velocities 225-439 m/s between 21:00-22:15 UTC.

Saturday 8 June 2019, SWPC/NOAA issued a warning for a minor Geomagnetic Storm, NOAA Level G1, at 18:47 UTC. Preliminary local K index estimated for Ebro Station reached a value of 5 for the two consecutive three-hourly intervals 15 – 21 (Figure 42).

Figure 42. Preliminary local K index estimated for Ebro Station for 8 June 2019.

The real-time HF-INT method of TechTIDE detected a TID with a dominant period of about 125 minutes for the northern European stations. The TID propagated dominantly southward and lasted from 20:00 (UT) of 8 of June to 4:00 (UT) of 9 of June (Figure 43).

Figure 43. LSTID detected by HF-INT for Dourbes, Belgium (DB049), Juliusruh, Germany (JR055), Pruhonice, Czech Republic (PQ052) and Chilton, UK (RL052).

The movie available at https://twitter.com/Tech_TIDE/status/1138420802385326080 shows the southward propagating event observed from 20:00 of 8 of June to 4:00 UT of 9 of June 2019. This LSTID was observed for the northern European stations for long time (8 hours) and very fewer time (2 hours) was possible to observe in the southern station of Ebro in Spain (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Snapshot for the disturbance propagation of the LSTID detected by the HF-INT method for the night of 8-9 June 2019.

At a first glance, the results provided by the HF-TID method in TechTIDE reports moderate to strong TID activity over Europe in the links DB049-JR055 and DB049-JR055 near by 21 UT but with short duration.

The HF-TID method indicated a passage of a LSTID on JR-PQ radio path at 2475 kHz on 8th June from 20:00 to 24:00 UT with WaveLength of 1433 km and WavePeriod of 163 minutes and another LSTID passage from 00:00 to 04:00 UT of 9th June with WaveLength 1457 km and WavePeriod of 160 minutes.

LSTID activity was detected over Europe by HTI on 8-9 of June 2019. In Juliusruh (JR055) Germany, the disturbance was first detected on June 8 at about 20:00 UT and lasted for about 8 hours (Figure 45, left). Over Dourbes (DB049) Belgium, the disturbance was first detected at about 23:45 UT and lasted for about 4 hours (Figure 45, right).

Figure 45. HTI detection of LSTID over two European stations for 8 to 9 June 2019.

LSTID activity over these northern European Digisonde stations was characterized with periods of about 160 min. (Figure 46). No LSTID activity was registered over Pruhonice (PQ052) Czech Republic and Ebro (EB040) in Spain.

Figure 46. LSTID activity as detected by HTI on the night of 8 to 9 June 2019.

CDSS indicators detected LSTIDs with periods higher than 60 min and propagating southward over the Czech Republic on 8 June between 19:45-22:00 UT on both 3.59 MHz and 4.65 MHz sounding frequencies (Figure 47). Horizontal velocity of the detected TIDs was in the range 211-319 m/s. However, no significant TID activity was observed with the CDSS method for 9 June 2019.

Figure 47. LSTID activity observed over the western part of the Czech Republic on evening hours of 8 June 2019 on CDSS sounding frequencies of 3.59 MHz (on the left) and 4.65 MHz (on the right).

The research group of Astronomy and GEomatics (gAGE/UPC) from UPC has elaborated a study using the AATR index as a mean to evaluate the ionosphere activity during the days from June 3th to June 10th (Day of the Year from 154 to 161, respectively). AATR values (in TECUs/min) are shown in the Figure 48 left. AATR index detects high ionospheric activity during the last hours of June 8th (DoY 159) and the beginning of June 9th (DoY 160), in the aurorae region (between the polar magnetic region and high magnetic latitudes), especially for northernmost receivers (KIRU and ARJ6), with values higher than 1 TECUs/min. A noticeable slight increase of ionospheric activity is observed at the end of June 4th and beginning of June 5th (DoY 155 and 156). Nevertheless, this activity is recorded within the AATR normal/typical behaviour region, reaching values around 0.2 TECUs/min.

Figure 48. Left plot depicts the AATR index values for receivers KIRU, ARJ6, UME6 and VIS0 for days of the year 154 - 162 of 2019. Right plot shows AATR index values for days of the year from 154 to 162 of 2019 with respect to the geographic latitude and the magnetic DIP angle (in degrees).

Figure 48 right presents the AATR values for a set of 166 GNSS receivers. For this plot, AATR values are referenced with respect to the geographic latitude as well as for the magnetic DIP angle (both in degrees). According to this figure, AATR detects moderate (from 0.5 up to 1 TECUs/min) and high (higher than 1 TECUs/min) ionosphere activity for receivers located at high magnetic latitudes (greater than 75). This confirms the ionosphere activity is present within the aurorae region.

5. Summary and additional remarks

The report presented the TID activity in TechTIDE for different methodologies including a specification of statistical limits, based on which the TID disturbance are characterized with different levels of importance for different methods and categories. The different methodologies feed the [TechTIDE warning system](#) [RD-7] and are classified according to the different categories as **indicators**, **LSTID detection methods**, and **MSTID detection methods**, whose metrics are provided in Table 7, Table 8, and Table 9 respectively.

The results of the different methodologies also furnish the information of [TechTIDE Activity Report](#) [RD-7] which can be summarized in the Table 10, Table 11, and Table 12 for LSTID detection methods, and MSTID detection methods, and indicators respectively.

Table 10. Activity Report for the **LSTID Detection Methods**.

Method	Indication	Results
HF-TID	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
HF-INT	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Ebro	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Dourbes	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Juliusruh	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Athens	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Hermanus	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
1D dEDD over Grahamstown	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details

Table 11. Activity Report for the **MSTID Detection Methods**.

Method	Indication	Results
MSTID index	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details
CDSS	TID activity/No activity/Uncertainty	Click here for details

Table 12. Activity Report for the ionospheric disturbance **indicators**.

Method	Indication	Results
TEC gradients	Low/Medium/Strong	Click here for details
AATR	Low/Medium/Strong	Click here for details
Ionospheric Background Conditions	Positive/Median/Negative	200km, 300km, 400km, 500km

The [TechTIDE Activity Report](#) [RD-7] has been developed according to user needs as provided in the two users workshops held in Neusterlitz, Germany, on May 2019 (1st TechTIDE User Workshop; MS#9 [AD-1]) and in Prague, Czech Republic, on October 2019 (1st TechTIDE User Workshop; MS#10 [AD-1]). According to the user needs, [TechTIDE Activity Report](#) [RD-7] provides three standards for the MSTID and MSTID detection methods; **TID activity**, **No activity**, and **Uncertainty**; and three standards for the disturbance **indicators**; **Low**, **Medium**, and **Strong** for both TEC gradients and AATR index, and **Positive**, **Median**, and **Negative** for the Ionospheric Background Conditions.

User needs also requested additional geophysical information for overall assessment of current conditions of the ionospheric environment which are triggers or drivers of the TID activity [RD-3]. Such a geophysical information also furnish the information of [TechTIDE Activity Report](#) [RD-7] which can be summarized in the Table 13, and Table 14 for Astronomical and Atmospheric Drivers, and Geospace conditions respectively.

Table 13. Astronomical and Atmospheric Drivers.

Driver	
Atmospheric Infrasound	Click here for details
Earthquake	Click here for details
Solar and lunar eclipse	Next solar eclipses will occur on 2019 Dec 26 , 2020 Jun 21 , 2020 Dec 14 Next lunar eclipses will occur on 2020 Jan 10 , 2020 Jun 5 , 2020 Jul 5 , 2020 Nov 30
Solar terminator location	Click here for details

Table 14. Geospace conditions.

Driver	
CME/HSS (Space weather activity originated from the Sun)	Click to get CME for the last 7 days! Click to get HSS for the last 7 days!
Solar Flares (NOAA SWPC/GOES)	Click here for details
AE Indices	Click here for details
Dst Index	Click here for details
Kp Index	Click here for details

Finally, results of the performance of the different TID detection methods have been provided for retrospective and near-real-time analysis and for different scenarios (Section 4). Table 15 and Table 16 show a summary of the results of the detection of events for the ionospheric disturbance indicators, and LSTID methods respectively. No comparisons are provided for MSTID methods because the MSTID index was not available for near real-time operation. However, CDSS observed strong activity for the events of April and June of 2019.

Table 15. Comparison of the results of the detection of events by ionospheric disturbance Indicators. Note that NA NRT means that the method was not available in near real-time for that interval.

Event	Driver	Indicators		
		AATR	TEC Gradient	Ionospheric Background
7-8/09/17	CME	Strong	Strong	Positive to Negative
23-24/04/19	CME – CH HSS	Medium - Low	Low	NA NRT
3-5/06/19	CME – CH HSS	Low	NA NRT	NA NRT
8-9/06/19	CH HSS	Medium - Low	NA NRT	NA NRT

Table 16. Comparison of the results of the detection of events by LSTID methods. Note that NA NRT means that the method was not available in near real-time for that interval. Note also that the levels of activity for HF-INT method correspond to those of the first release (Section 0).

Event	Driver	LSTID detection methods			
		HF-TID	HF-INT	LSTID index	HTI
7-8/09/17	CME	Strong	Strong - Moderate	No results provided.	Strong - Moderate
23-24/04/19	CME – CH HSS	Strong - Moderate	Strong	NA NRT	Moderate
3-5/06/19	CME – CH HSS	Moderate - Weak	Strong - Moderate	NA NRT	NA NRT
8-9/06/19	CH HSS	Strong - Moderate	Strong - Moderate	NA NRT	Strong - Moderate

Overall the presented results are coherent among the different categories of methodologies.